

Test of Current Viscosity Theories for Dilute Polymer Solutions from Light Scattering Data

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The consequences of the equations developed by Flory, by Kurata, Stockmayer and Roig as also by Ptitsyn to take care of intramolecular volume effect were checked in a previous paper using α_n , the viscometric expansion co-efficient. The Flory plot, K-S-R plot and Ptitsyn plot were all found to be fairly linear as expected from theory but the lines did not pass through the origin, the Flory plot showing the maximum deviation in most cases. In the present paper it is found that replacement of viscometric expansion coefficients, α_n^3 , by coefficients of the radii of gyration, α_g^3 , obtained from light scattering data available in literature, does not substantially improve the agreement between theoretical relations and experimental values. It has also been found that the equation deduced by Palit which predicts a linear dependence of $100 \rho_0[\eta] + \ln M$ on $M^{2/3}$ with a slope of the order of 10^{-2} provides a good fit with experimental data in most of the cases.

The predictions of the theory of Flory^{1,2}—eq. (1), Kurata *et al.*³—eq. (2) and Ptitsyn⁴—eq. (3) have been the subject of a large number of investigations with respect to their experimental validity.

$$\alpha^5 - \alpha^3 = CM^\dagger \quad \dots (1)$$

$$(\alpha^3 - \alpha) \left(1 + \frac{1}{3\alpha^2} \right)^{3/2} = C'M^\dagger \quad \dots (2)$$

$$[(4.68 \alpha^2 - 3.68)^{3/2} - 1] = C''M^\dagger \quad \dots (3)$$

In all these investigations^{1,5,6,7} including those by the present authors^{8,9}, α values derived from viscosity data have been used and it has been found that these theories suffer from various limitations. It was therefore considered worthwhile to re-investigate the validity of the above theories using α_g values where α_g is a ratio of the actual gyration radii to the gyration radii in a θ -solvent as determined by light scattering. That is $\alpha_g^3 = (\bar{S}^2/\bar{S}_0^2)^{3/2}$. Normally following Flory-Fox α_g^3 is supposed to be equal to α_η^3 though this identity is not

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valid as shown theoretically by Kurata *et al.*¹⁰ and Ptitsyn *et al.*¹¹ and experimentally by Krigbaum *et al.*¹² and by Schulz *et al.*^{13,14}. The same source of data has been utilised to test the following viscosity molecular weight relationship deduced by Palit¹⁵

$$100 \rho_0[\eta] + \ln M = K_1 M^{2/3} + K_2 \quad \dots (4)$$

Graphical Test of the Four Equations

A. Addition Polymers

1. *Polyisoprene*: The data of Bristow *et al.*¹⁶ in tetrahydrofuran (Fig. 1) at 25° are utilised. The values of α_s are found to increase with increase of molecular weight indicating increased expansion of the molecule. Analysis of Flory Relation: According to Flory equation plot of $\alpha_s^5 - \alpha_s^3$ against $M^{1/2}$ is expected to give a straight line passing through the origin. Such plot, (marked 1, Fig. 1) though good linear, does not pass through the origin. Abscissa intercept corresponds to $M \simeq 8.14 \times 10^4$ (least square method has been applied in all such

Fig. 1. Polyisoprene in tetrahydrofuran at 25°.

10. M. Kurata and H. Yamakawa, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1958, **29**, 311.
11. O. B. Ptitsyn and Yu. Ye. Eizner, *Z. Techn. Fiz.*, 1959, **29**, 1117.
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13. G. V. Schulz and R. Kirste, *Z. Physik Chem. (Frankfurt)*, 1961, **27**, 301.
14. G. V. Schulz and R. Kirste, *Z. Physik Chem. (Frankfurt)*, 1961, **30**, 171.
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16. G. M. Bristow, *J. Polymer Sci.*, 1963, **A1**, 2261.

cases). Analysis of Kurata *et al.*'s relation : Plot of $(\alpha_s^3 - \alpha_s) \left(1 + \frac{1}{3\alpha_s^2}\right)^{3/2}$ versus M^{\dagger} (marked 2) is fairly good linear but it does not pass through the origin and gives an abscissa intercept corresponding to $M \simeq 2.96 \times 10^4$. It is apparent that the data fit in better with K-S-R equation.

Fig. 2. Polymethyl methacrylate in butylchloride at 40°.

Analysis of Ptitsyn relation : According to Ptitsyn, plot of $[(4.68 \alpha_s^2 - 3.68)^{3/2} - 1]$ vs. M^{\dagger} is expected to give a straight line passing through the origin. Such a plot (marked 3) is poorly linear and does not pass through the origin but gives an abscissa intercept corresponding to $M \simeq 4.67 \times 10^4$. This indicates that like the other two equations Ptitsyn equation has also got limited applicability in this case but it is in a sense better than that due to Flory as its range of applicability is greater.

Analysis of Palit Relation : According to Palit equation plot of $100 \rho_0 [\eta] + \ln M$ ag. $M^{2/3}$ is expected to give a straight line of slope of the order of 10^{-2} . Poorly linear plot (marked 4) is obtained but with the fairly correct theoretical slope of 9.5×10^{-2} .

2. *Polymethyl Methacrylate* : The data of Schulz and Kirste¹⁴ are utilised. The values of α_s are found to increase with increase of solvent power indicating increased expansion of the molecule.

In Butyl chloride at 40° (Fig. 2) all the first three plots are scattered. Abscissa intercepts correspond to $M \simeq 0.0431 \times 10^6$, 0.0103×10^6 and 0.0275×10^6 respectively. Good linear plot according to Palit equation is obtained with a slope of 0.5×10^{-2} .

Fig. 3. PMMA in butylchloride at 44°.

At 44° (Fig. 3), the first three plots are scattered as before with abscissa intercepts at $M \simeq 0.0298 \times 10^6$, 0.0007×10^6 and 0.0124×10^6 respectively. Good linear plot according to Palit equation is obtained with a slope of 0.51×10^{-2} .

At 48° (Fig. 4), the scatter of the experimental plots is also similar. The Flory equation gives an abscissa intercept corresponding to $M \simeq 0.024 \times 10^6$, while the K-S-R equation gives a small ordinate intercept and the Ptitsyn equation gives a small abscissa intercept and thus may be said to be more or less valid. A good linear plot is obtained in case of Palit equation with slope of 0.59×10^{-2} .

3. *Polystyrene*: The data of Oth and Desreux¹⁷ are utilised. In M.E.K. containing 5% methanol (Fig. 5), the Flory plot is good linear while the K-S-R and Ptitsyn plots are fairly good linear. But while the K-S-R equation passes through the origin, the Flory and Ptitsyn plots give abscissa intercepts corresponding to $M \simeq 8.77 \times 10^4$ and 1.96×10^4 respectively. Very good linear plot according to Palit equation is obtained with a slope of 0.96×10^{-2} . In chloroform (Fig. 6), the Flory plot is scattered while the K-S-R and Ptitsyn

plots are more or less good linear. The Flory equation gives an abscissa intercept corresponding to $M \simeq 2.51 \times 10^4$ while the other two equations give ordinate intercepts. Very good linear plot according to Palit equation is obtained with a slope of 0.19×10^{-2} .

Fig. 4. PMMA in butylchloride at 48°.

In M.E.K. (Fig. 7), the Flory plot is poorly linear and the K-S-R and Ptitsyn plots are good linear. None of them passes through the origin but gives ordinate intercepts. Very good linear plot according to Palit equation is obtained with a slope of 1.2×10^{-2} .

The data of Notley *et al.*¹⁸ are utilised. In cyclohexane at 43° (Fig. 8), the first two plots are scattered while the Ptitsyn plot is fairly good linear. None of them passes through the origin but they give abscissa intercepts corresponding to $M \simeq 44.7 \times 10^4$, 34.19×10^4 and 39.93×10^4 respectively. Palit equation is not verifiable because of the lack of $[\eta]$ data.

In cyclohexane at 57° (Fig. 9), the Flory plot is fairly good linear, the K-S-R plot is scattered while the Ptitsyn plot is good linear but they give abscissa intercepts corresponding to $M \simeq 46.47 \times 10^4$, 30×10^4 and 39.26×10^4 respectively.

In toluene at 20° (Fig. 10), the Flory plot is highly scattered and the K-S-R and Ptitsyn plots are also scattered. They give abscissa intercepts corresponding to $M \simeq 63.52 \times 10^4$, 10.96×10^4 and 47.25×10^4 respectively.

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18. N. T. Notley and P. Debye, *J. Polymer Sci.*, 1955, **17**, 99.

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Fig. 5. Polystyrene in methyl ethyl ketone : methanol mixture (95 : 5 v/v) at 25°.

Fig. 6. Polystyrene in chloroform at 25°.

Fig. 7. PS in methyl ethyl ketone at 25°.

Fig. 8. PS in cyclohexane at 43°.

Fig. 9. PS in cyclohexane at 57°.

Fig. 10. PS in toluene at 20°.

Fig. 11. Polyvinyl acetate in M.E.K. at 25°.

Fig. 12. Cellulose tricarbanilate in Dioxan at 20°.

4. *Polyvinyl Acetate*: The data of Schultz¹⁹ are utilised. The Flory and Ptitsyn plots are scattered and they do not pass through the origin; but give abscissa intercepts corresponding to $M \simeq 19.68 \times 10^4$ and 5.49×10^4 (Fig. 11). The K-S-R plot is fairly good linear and passes through the origin. Palit plot is very good linear with a slope of 2.67×10^{-2} (in M.E.K.).

TABLE I
Summary of Results

Polymer	Solvent (θ -solvent)	Temp. °C	Linearity and Abscissa intercepts in terms of M				Best Linear Eq.	Eq. that passes through the origin among 1, 2 and 3
			Flory plot Eq. 1	K-S-R plot Eq. 2	Ptitsyn plot Eq. 3	Palit plot Eq. 4 $K_1, 10^2$		
Poly- isoprene	Tetrahydrofuran (Butyl-ether 60 : Butanol 40)	25	Good 8.14×10^4	fairly good 2.96×10^4	Poor 4.67×10^4	poor 9.5	1	None'
PMMA	Butyl Chloride ($T_\theta = 35.4$)	40	scattered $.0431 \times 10^6$	scattered $.0103 \times 10^6$	scattered $.0275 \times 10^6$	good .5	4	Do
		44	scattered $.0298 \times 10^6$	scattered $.0007 \times 10^6$	scattered $.0124 \times 10^6$	good .51	4	Do
		48	scattered $.024 \times 10^6$	scattered small*	scattered 0	very good .59	4	3, 2
PS	MEK + MeOH(5%) (MEK + MeOH 11%)	25	good 8.77×10^4	fairly good 0	fairly good 1.96×10^4	very good .96	4, 1	2
	Chloroform (MEK + MeOH 11%)	25	scattered 2.51×10^4	good *	good small*	very good .19	4, 3	3
	MEK (MEK + MeOH 11%)	25	poor *	good *	good *	very good 1, 2	4, 2, 3	None
PS	Cyclohexane ($T_\theta = 34^\circ$)	43	scattered 44.7×10^4	scattered 34.19×10^4	fairly good 39.93×10^4	—	3	None
		57	fairly good 46.47×10^4	scattered 30×10^4	good 39.26×10^4	—	3	Do
PS	Toluene Cyclohexane ($T_\theta = 34^\circ$)	20	highly scattered 63.52×10^4	scattered 10.96×10^4	scattered 47.25×10^4	—	None	Do
Polyvinyl Acetate	MEK (73% Meiso-PK + 27% Heptane)	25	scattered 19.68×10^4	fairly good 0	scattered 5.49×10^4	very good 2.67	4, 2	2
Cellulose Tricarba- nilate.	Dioxan (Dioxane/56% MeOH).	20	scattered 50 D.P.	fairly good small*	fairly good 0	—	2	3

* Stands for ordinate intercept.

19. A. R. Schultz, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 3422.

B. *Semisynthetics from Cellulose*

Cellulose Tricarbanilate: The data of Burchard²⁰ are utilised. The Flory plot is scattered while the K-S-R and Ptitsyn plots are fairly good linear. (Fig. 12). The Ptitsyn plot passes through the origin while the K-S-R plot gives a small ordinate intercept and the Flory plot gives an abscissa intercept corresponding to a Degree of Polymerisation value of 50. Plot according to Palit equation is not shown as $[\eta]$ data are not available.

DISCUSSION

In the 12 different polymer-solvent systems analysed, it is observed (Table 1) that as regards linearity of the $F(\alpha_s)$ vs. $M^{\frac{1}{2}}$ plot, Ptitsyn plot is found to be the best in four cases, K-S-R plot is the best in three cases while Flory plot is best in two cases only. The data for the other three systems are highly scattered for all the equations. Hence from the stand point of linearity there is not much to choose between. As regards the criteria of passing through the origin, the K-S-R and Ptitsyn equation are satisfactory in three cases while the Flory equation is not satisfactory even in a single case. In the 8 different polymer-solvent systems studied Palit plot is very good linear in 5 cases and good linear in 2 cases with the right theoretical slope of the order of 10^{-2} in 3 out of altogether 8 cases.

CONCLUSION

The general conclusion is that the Flory equation suffers from the limitation that it is valid generally in the high molecular weight range. The K-S-R and Ptitsyn expressions are better suited to interpret the molecular expansion of most of the polymers discussed. Where all of them give an abscissa intercept, the value is always found to be the greatest in the case of Flory equation, and in the case of K-S-R equation it is always the least. Thus K-S-R equation based on an equivalent ellipsoid model is the best. This is in conformity with our results obtained from viscometric and osmometric studies on poly m-methyl styrene⁹ and also from data on other different polymer-solvent systems as obtained from literature⁸. In practically all cases a linear relation between $100\rho_0[\eta] + \ln M$ and $M^{2/3}$ is observed as expected from the equation deduced by Palit and the observed slope agrees within an order of magnitude with the theoretically predicted slope of 10^{-2} .

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